

SIZE-PLANNING AND URBAN PLANNING OF BUILDINGS IN SEISMICALLY ACTIVE REGIONS REQUIREMENTS FOR SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: *This article discusses the basics of micro-zoning and the requirements for urban planning solutions in earthquake-prone areas. It describes how the spatial dimensions of a building affect its earthquake resistance. In addition, there is information about the main considerations in the preparation of the master plan of the city in seismically active areas.*

Key words: *seismically active area, micro-zoning, urban planning rules, earthquake resistance of the building, green areas, master plan, underground water.*

It is known that the geography of earthquakes is formed in such a way that almost 85% of the urban population of our republic is concentrated in these seismically active areas. This, in turn, imposes strict requirements on urban planning. In seismically active areas, taking into account the danger to human life, the tasks aimed at fulfilling these requirements should be solved constructively. At this point, it is appropriate to briefly touch upon the effect of the building configuration (volumetric and spatial dimensions) on seismic strength.

It is known that the larger the volume-spatial dimensions of the building, the more its characteristics change: the price increases, the number (volume) of technological processes increases, the weight increases, etc. k. The smaller the size of the building, the smaller its weight and, of course, the value of the inertial forces that arise during an earthquake. In addition, the size of these building profiles is much smaller compared to the floor surface of the building, and in such conditions,

static (dynamic) forces are distributed to a large number of wall constructions that externalize the spatial system of the building.

The increase in the volume-spatial dimensions of the building, in addition to the increase in its price, complicates the working conditions of constructions that externalize the volume-planning system of the building. In the study of the consequences of many earthquakes, it was known that buildings with relatively small spatial dimensions were less damaged.

As the height of the building increases, its period of free (private) oscillation also increases. Usually, a change in the period of free oscillation of a building leads to a change in the response of the building and corresponding stresses at the upper and lower levels. It is known that the period of dominant vibration of an earthquake depends on the geological conditions of the furnace surroundings, and it lasts 0.1-2 seconds. Increasing the height of the building (and, accordingly, the vibration period) will move it away from the dominant vibration period of the earthquake. This does not mean that the problems will be eliminated in this direction. According to many experts, from the point of view of the seismic stability of buildings, it is desirable that the number of floors does not exceed 15 floors (with the increase in the height of the buildings, the overturning stresses that affect them during an earthquake also increase). If the size of the building is large, regardless of its symmetrical and simple appearance, the building cannot resist the impact of the seismic wave as a whole body. That is why the normative documents specify the limit values of the dimensions of the buildings.

When designing earthquake-resistant building structures, it is more important to pay attention to the geometric proportions of the building system than its geometric dimensions. The ratio of the length to the width of the building is important in arriving at an architectural solution, the extended form is not appropriate for buildings. The structural solution (planned density) of the building

is an important factor in ensuring the earthquake resistance of buildings during an earthquake.

It is known from the history of architecture that in the past, the number and size of the elements and constructions that externalized the load-bearing basis of buildings and structures were significantly larger than those of today's buildings and structures. Over time, the improvement of the construction calculation methodology, the size of the elements that make up the load-bearing base of buildings, and the level of aesthetic requirements aimed at reducing their number, the load-bearing base of buildings has reached the current state. In many cases, aesthetic acceptance conflicts with earthquake design requirements. The structural solution or plan density of buildings is understood as the size measured by the ratio of the sum of the surfaces of vertical load-bearing elements: columns, walls, single joints to the total floor area. In today's modern construction, among all types of buildings, frame buildings (with columns made of metal) are projects with the lowest planned density. However, if the requirements leading to the technological limitation of building height deserve special attention, one of the next requirements is a significant decrease in the density of buildings in urban planning. This creates a good opportunity to eliminate the consequences of the earthquake in the short term.

It is known that the construction of new cities and the expansion of existing ones, the placement of industrial enterprises, buildings and communications can be carried out only in emergency cases and on the specified lands in accordance with the land legislation and in accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Since such large-scale activities require a lot of funds, this area should be based on production and socio-economic aspects, as well as satisfy a number of requirements.

When choosing any territory, local, hydrogeological, technical-economic, sanitary-hygienic and similar indicators should be taken into account. In urban planning, it is especially important to take into account climatic conditions and wind

direction. Under normal conditions, the residential zone of the city should be located in relation to the industrial zone in such a way that the direction of the wind to the residential zone should not correspond to the direction of the toxic gases that are likely to poison the atmosphere in the industrial zone. Wind direction is one of the most important factors in preventing the risk of environmental pollution due to damage to industrial facilities caused by earthquakes in seismically active regions. Another important factor is the terrain.

The effect of seismic impact on buildings and structures during an earthquake depends on the relief of the natural area, and the role of taking this factor into account in urban planning is incomparable. When the slope of the natural relief increases, the complexity of the relief can lead to an increase in the intensity of the seismic impact and floods during an earthquake: flooding of areas due to damage to water pipes and sewers, and other negative consequences.

One of the main factors in choosing a territory for construction is the engineering-geological conditions of the place. Above, we discussed in detail the relationship between the engineering-geological conditions of the area and the intensity of the seismic impact during an earthquake. It is known that the effectiveness of the use of landscape architecture methods in the placement of residential areas of cities and micro districts depends on the level of comprehensive consideration of sanitary and hygienic requirements in the design of these areas. In particular, controlling the wind regime by building or placing buildings according to the wind pattern is an important aspect of the issue. This situation is especially important after the earthquake, at the stage of restoration and repair of buildings and structures in this area. In large industrial districts, chemical plants and other production technology accidents involving substances that have a toxic effect on the environment can cause great damage to the environment and especially to people as a result of damage or destruction caused by an earthquake. In order to prevent such an unpleasant situation from happening, it is necessary to achieve smooth fulfillment

of the above-mentioned sanitary and hygienic requirements when placing residential areas in relation to industrial districts. In addition to the correct placement of buildings and structures on the natural terrain, it is especially important to choose the correct direction of the wind (wind flower), if necessary, to change the direction of the wind and take measures to neutralize air pollution, during the period of restoration of buildings after an earthquake.

At the stage of designing buildings in residential districts, the level of insulation is determined by special sanitary standards. Greening of residential territories in these areas should not only take into account the standard duration of insolation, but also take into account the fact that the environment does not overheat, that is, the reduction of heat from radiation. Especially, this situation has a primary impact on the bacteriological condition in this residential area when an earthquake occurs on hot days of the year.

In general, in the design of residential areas, it is necessary to pay attention to the improvement of living and working conditions, and in this regard, the use of protective measures of urban planning, as well as a comprehensive approach to the sanitary and hygienic condition of the environment in the event of an earthquake. The consequences of many earthquakes have shown that the closest "companions" of earthquakes are strong fires. The main factor in reducing the damage caused by fire during an earthquake is the thoughtful use of special measures (methods) of urban planning. It is appropriate to involve specialists in the field of engineering seismology and anti-seismic construction in this process, not at the stage of eliminating the consequences of the earthquake, but at the stage of drawing up the master plans of construction in the region.

Master plans of industrial enterprises, cities and residential settlements must be developed taking into account the results of seismic zoning. Especially in seismically active regions of 8 and 9 points, the results of seismic micro-zoning must

be taken into account when drawing up master plans of large cities and developing industrial zones.

As a rule, it is not recommended to build buildings and structures in areas with a seismic activity of 9 points and above (also specified in normative documents). If there is a need for the construction of important public economic facilities in this zone, construction works can be carried out with the permission of the Republican "Davarkitekqurilish" committee and other government bodies. In regions with a seismic activity of 9 points, it is recommended to limit construction facilities other than the processing of local material resources, services to the population, new scientific research and design institutes necessary for the region, higher and secondary special educational institutions. The construction of objects of this type is allowed if it is feasible from the technical and economic point of view.

Large massifs in the 8-9 seismically active zones in the city must be separated by transport highways or green zones. These zones prevent the spread of fire that occurs during an earthquake, and this situation makes it possible to quickly evacuate the population without casualties. If the epicentral zone is likely to be located within the city, then the green zone must be located.

Public centers and public buildings, sports facilities, hospitals, schools and other children's institutions where people gather a lot should be placed in a seismically favorable zone. Public catering establishments and food trading centers in 9-point seismic activity zones are usually located in separate low-rise buildings. Buildings and structures should be placed in seismically unfavorable zones and in territories with poor soil conditions and groundwater levels close to the surface of the earth, so that the destruction (collapse) of such buildings and structures does not endanger people's lives, damage valuable equipment, technological processes should not stop and cause environmental damage due to accidents. In the development of the master plan of industrial enterprises, it is necessary to choose extremely favorable conditions from the seismic point of view for buildings with technological

processes that are at risk of explosion, if the life of employees participating in production is threatened as a result of an accident, and for nuclear power plants.

Limit values of the sizes of residential, public and industrial buildings and structures are given in QMQ 2.01.03-19

It is recommended to adopt a technological process with a horizontal scheme in the design of industrial enterprises in areas with high seismic activity, soil conditions and the level of underground water near the surface of the earth.

Buildings and structures (energy and water supply systems, firefighting depots, communication points), large industrial complexes, sports facilities where a large number of people gather at the same time, and similar buildings, which need to be in operation during the period of the end of the earthquake, are included in the master plan when developing the master plan. In addition to being in the gray zone from the climatological and seismic point of view, special importance should be paid to the location of the buildings in relation to each other. The territory where these buildings and structures are located should be outside the zone of flooding due to damage of water structures during an earthquake. If this requirement is not met, the construction of a special protective hydro technical facility is required.

In such conditions, it is appropriate to limit the density of buildings and structures (population) in the master plan.

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